

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DENG****FIRST NAME: ACHAI****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

THE ESSENTIALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) SUMMARY

The Euclid University ACA-401 course module aims to prepare students for academic writing. The module starts with period one and includes the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack edited by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2019), and the video titled *Understanding Templates and Styles for ACA-401* (EUCLID 2016). These course materials, together, present concepts essential to academic writing at Euclid University.

The coursepack material is divided into nine chapters; each covering a different, but related topic. The first chapter explores essay writing; the process of starting an essay, researching a topic of interest, organizing around ideas, referencing, and editing. The second chapter is on plagiarism, and so explains what plagiarism means, examples of it, and how to avoid it. It delves into the use of citation-whether short, long, or paraphrased-to give credit to the rightful author. The third chapter relays rules of thumb related to writing that are helpful to the writer; it is the shortest of all the chapters. The fourth chapter then opens on the topic of literature review; it examines words of similarity, such as “its” and “it’s”, that are often wrongly used (EUCLID 2019, 18). The fifth chapter explores the necessity of a style guide; it gives reason why a style guide is helpful. The sixth chapter is among the longer chapters; it weighs American English against British English by looking into differences in; punctuation, spelling, pronunciation, word meanings, word preferences and the like. The seventh chapter examines corrected papers; it makes clear what has been corrected and why it has been corrected. The eighth chapter unveils in detail the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and its usage. Lastly, the ninth chapter takes to point Latin abbreviations and expressions commonly used in writing. The video on the other hand

focuses on how to use the Turabian style in Microsoft Word. It includes elements of U.S. and U.K. English; in-text citation and footnoting; as well as aspects of grammar and punctuation (for example the use of the comma).

2) COURSEPACK ENGAGEMENT

In this section, I will engage with the course material with a primary focus on the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack material, with an occasional referencing to the video. It will unfold on a chapter by chapter basis, focusing on the concepts covered in the selected chapters.

a) Essay Writing

Chapter one covers the basis of essay writing: starting the essay, researching, organizing, writing, referencing, and editing. Starting the essay is certainly not a linear process; I, for one, often start my essays from the body and allow the introduction and conclusion to gradually reveal themselves. I sometimes do not take enough time analyzing the question and just jump into writing and researching while continually looking back to the question. I think it will be helpful for me to spend sufficient time analyzing an essay question from the very beginning, rather than coming back to the question repeatedly. I, nonetheless, appreciate that the coursepack mentions that the steps of writing are “in no strict order” (EUCLID 2019, 1). Notwithstanding, I think it is great to have a plan from the beginning, it really helps to guide the writing process. Throughout most of primary school, my English teachers advised to write out a plan as rough work before beginning a composition; to jot down key ideas and supporting ideas. It is helpful for clarity and organization; when I do not have a plan, I find myself mixing in ideas within paragraphs.

Researching a topic links with understanding the question, because it is needful to have relevant sources for consultation. The chapter also stipulates the importance of reading with a purpose (EUCLID 2019, 2). I suppose this applies to life generally, I hear people many times say, “start with the end in mind,” and “you need to have a vision.” It equally applies to writing, if anything- because it helps with giving direction to the writing and allows the laying out of the first draft. The first draft for me is usually exciting, I write on the chosen topic, freely, without bothering too much about grammar, diction, and other minute details. I just write and allow all kinds of ideas and co-relations to materialize on paper. Thereafter, the editing process begins; it can be a bit agonizing, but it is certainly worthwhile.

b) Plagiarism

Chapter two examines the definition of plagiarism, examples of it, and how to avoid it. Plagiarism occurs “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Examples of it include: using other people’s words and ideas as your own; handing in as your own a paper someone

else has written; using words from the internet; and not giving the rightful author credit due to him/her (ibid.). I think it is important that the material mentioned the unethical aspect of plagiarism. I remember one of my classmates asking to go through a math paper I had highly scored in, I gave it to him. Consequently, some exchange students who had befriended me rebuked me saying, “you worked really hard on that, he’s just going to copy your work.” I did not think it was the case (because it was math), but I could see how my friends connected it to plagiarism being taking credit for something someone else worked hard on- strenuously, agonizingly even. It had not occurred to me in that sense before: I mostly thought of plagiarism as a great disservice to oneself; robbing from oneself the opportunity to increase understanding in the topic of writing, and stunting one’s development in the skills related to writing and researching.

That aside, I also appreciate that this chapter explains when to cite and when not to cite. I found it clarifying to read that when information stated is common knowledge, it does not need citation (EUCLID 2019, 10) and “if it is repeated in many different sources...assume it is common knowledge” (ibid.).

c) U.S./U.K. English

The sixth chapter on U.S. and U.K. English, of all the chapters, most captivated me. Particularly, because it starts out with giving reasons why U.S. English is becoming more prevalent as compared to U.K. English (it felt like I was reading a page on international relations). I was familiar with most of the differences, but some aspects covered in the chapter were altogether new to me.

I am familiar with differences in spelling, which is altogether obvious when I type the word 'colour' on Microsoft, only to be corrected on my spelling by the U.S. English proofreading mechanism. Also, I usually write “organisation” and not “organization.” Often, I put an “s” instead of “z”; as in the words “authorisation,” and “sanitisation.” However, with this matter, the language proof-reading setting is useful to correct based on whether I set proof-reading to either U.S. English or U.K. English. Differences in pronunciation of words with the same spelling was not all too new either. I remember saying with friends “tomato (‘to-ma-to’), tomato (‘to-meh-to’)” when implying we were talking about the same thing from different perspectives. I also usually quote with the U.K. style, using inverted commas instead of the U.S. style of using quotation marks. As I read through the course material, I noticed that there are a lot of other miniscule details that go into differentiating U.S. and U.K. English, confirming what was mentioned in the period one video.

The chapter also covered the influence of other languages/people groups on the English language, which I found fascinating to read on. I really had no idea that “shm” additions, as in ‘fat-shmat’ were related to the Jewish influence (EUCLID 2019, 33); I did not give it much thought before. I am glad this element was included in the paper, along with elements of political correctness, equality vocabulary, and so forth. It really reflects the influence of technological and social advancements on language as a generality, as in the words “blogging” and “chairperson” (EUCLID 2019, 32–33). I believe all these are

helpful for me to be able to relate with different audiences in writing; and to avoid unnecessary offence.

d) Chicago Style

The chapter on the Chicago style did a great deal to expose the Chicago: style and usage, page formatting, and, end/footnotes. Although, a lot of it is quite clear; it will require a lot of practice on my part. Notwithstanding, Zotero is an excellent tool to help with the referencing and citation. Additionally, the video for period one was excellent in giving a visual display of the Chicago Manual Style, including page formatting, intext citation, referencing, and some elements of grammar.

The style and usage are particularly helpful to link my writing to the Turabian style; I found it refreshing to go through rules that really apply in many ways to the English language as a generality. I find it inconveniencing if I have to go back constantly to see what a certain abbreviation or acronym stands for, but if it is introduced as I read a text, it is much easier for me to remember. Hence, I truly appreciate the rule of writing out in words in the first mention and putting the acronym in parenthesis (EUCLID 2019, 44). I also found clarity in the aspect of capitalization, particularly regarding geographical terms; for example, the capitalization of the “c” in “Central America and not central Europe, or central Asia” (EUCLID 2019, 45). The rules on compound words also brought to my attention a lot of rules that I generally took for granted. Made up compounds and serial compounds particularly stood out: the first, because I like making up compounds; the second, because I did not know I could write like this- “long- and short-term memory, 2-, 3-, and 10-min trials” (EUCLID 2019, 46). Furthermore, relating to prefixes, I would sometimes get confused on whether to write a word like “cooperate” with a hyphen, or not. I did not quite understand the rule stating that “if the prefix puts the same two letters together, a hyphen is *sometimes* [emphasis added] inserted” (ibid.). I also got clarity and re-enforcement on the use of italics and quotation marks. I was not aware that quotation marks are to be used in literal translations; I look forward to practicing this rule. Additionally, my friends and I liked to say “in quotes” while chatting to indicate irony; we used “scare quotes” verbally. I, therefore, rarely use scare quotes in writing, but I am glad to know they can be appropriately used in academic writing. I have also learned a lot in the section on quotations, that is, in how to add words to a quotation, emphasis, correcting errors, using block quotations, editing quotations and the like.

e) Literature Review

Chapter four on literature review was very relatable; it covers aspects of word order, elements of punctuation, and misuse of words that are similar in pronunciation. My youngest sister tends to use the word “I” instead of “me” as in the phrase, “me don't know.” I usually tell her to say, “I don't know.” I also tried to explain to her, in plain terms, that “I” is a subject pronoun, whereas “me” is an object pronoun. She did not quite understand, not yet anyway. For a long time, until later in college, I did not quite comprehend the aforementioned, and certainly not what the difference was between saying “Tom and I”

and “Tom and me” (EUCLID 2019, 22). Indeed, my “educated-self” has had moments of making such “embarrassing” mistakes.

The use of comma, colon, semi-colon, I was glad I had some practice in while helping my other sister do her English homework. Nonetheless, I must confess that I feel like I continuously need to improve my grammar. I also realized, while reading on literature review, that I have used “that” and “which” correctly; albeit, without being conscious of the fact that “ ‘that’ precedes only restrictive phrases, while ‘which’ usually precedes nonrestrictive phrases” (EUCLID 2019, 19).

On the errors of misusing words that are similar, I also relate. I have in times past confused “you’re” with “your”, and the like. The in-built corrections in Microsoft Word and Gmail have been magnificently helpful in keeping me from these errors; along with proof-reading (of course). It is not difficult for me to root out such errors after carefully reading through texts; for this reason, I understand why my primary school English teachers called them “careless mistakes.”

3) CONCLUSION

In all, the period one course materials are truly essential to prepare me for academic writing throughout my graduate program. They have recalled to me the process of essay writing, informed me on avoiding plagiarism, made clear to me the differences between U.S. and U.K. English, instructed me on how to use the Turabian style, and reminded me of general rules related to the English language.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2016. *Understanding Templates and Styles for ACA-401*.
<https://vimeo.com/157480457> (accessed on May 28, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack; Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.